

Model: all leafhoppers

\$uniformity

Asymptotic one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

data: simulationOutput\$scaledResiduals
D = 0.067926, p-value = 0.2181
alternative hypothesis: two-sided

\$dispersion

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals
fitted
vs. simulated

data: simulationOutput
dispersion = 1.2715, p-value = 0.392
alternative hypothesis: two.sided

\$outliers

DHARMA bootstrapped outlier test

data: simulationOutput
outliers at both margin(s) = 3, observations = 240, p-value = 0.
92
alternative hypothesis: two.sided
percent confidence interval:
0.000 0.025
sample estimates:
outlier frequency (expected: 0.0107083333333333)
0.0125

Model: Empoasca fabae

\$uniformity

Asymptotic one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

data: simulationOutput\$scaledResiduals
D = 0.035482, p-value = 0.966
alternative hypothesis: two-sided

\$dispersion

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals
fitted
vs. simulated

data: simulationOutput
dispersion = 1.132, p-value = 0.504
alternative hypothesis: two.sided

\$outliers

DHARMA bootstrapped outlier test

data: simulationOutput
outliers at both margin(s) = 0, observations = 196, p-value = 0.
44
alternative hypothesis: two.sided
percent confidence interval:
0.00000000 0.03061224
sample estimates:
outlier frequency (expected: 0.00989795918367347)
0

Model: Macrosteles quadrilineatus

\$uniformity

Asymptotic one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

data: simulationOutput\$scaledResiduals
D = 0.088202, p-value = 0.116
alternative hypothesis: two-sided

\$dispersion

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals
fitted
vs. simulated

data: simulationOutput
dispersion = 0.51452, p-value = 0.84
alternative hypothesis: two.sided

\$outliers

DHARMA bootstrapped outlier test

data: simulationOutput
outliers at both margin(s) = 0, observations = 183, p-value = 1
alternative hypothesis: two.sided
percent confidence interval:
0.0000000 0.0273224
sample estimates:
outlier frequency (expected: 0.00568306010928962)
0